

Preservation Monitoring

A Practical Guideline to Reducing Technology Risks

Written by members of the OPF interest group

International Comparison of Recommended File Formats (ICRFF)

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1. Introduction

The International Comparison of Recommended File Formats (ICRFF) was established in 2022 to discuss issues related to file formats.¹ Its first deliverable was a new resource that compares the accepted and preferred file formats used in digital preservation strategies at cultural heritage and research institutions globally. Following its success, this second work aims to advise how to monitor your organisation's portfolio of file formats and the applications used for their ingest, preservation, and dissemination.

The Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS) version 3² is a widely adopted standard by archives and libraries for defining the processes, objects, and terms for operating a digital archive. The OAIS defines a functional entity called “Preservation Planning”. This includes the function “Preservation Watch”, which receives input from further functions “Monitor Technology” and “Monitor Designated Community”, and sends communication to “Develop Preservation Strategies and Standards”. A related function is “Develop Packaging Designs and Preservation Plans”, which enables you to create new solutions for data preservation.

These five functions are crucial for the operation of an archive. They enable the institution to clearly define a preservation strategy and curate plans that consider past, current, and future changes within a technological environment. In practice, these functions assist, for example by selecting file formats for submission, storage, and dissemination, together with suitable software to enable this. They may also facilitate investment in developing any of the aforementioned technologies, or assist in selecting tools and resources for an emulation-based digital preservation strategy.

However, since OAIS is a reference model, it does not address how to monitor your data and infrastructure or assess risks to your mission. There is literature and methods available to assist with digital preservation practices, but we have been unable to identify actionable guidance on how to perform monitoring. This guideline has been developed to address this gap by offering a framework to assist your organisation in monitoring and assessing the risks of your historical data.

1.1. Purpose

The primary objective of this guideline is to assist organisations in facilitating seamless integration between the theories behind preservation planning and its practical implementation.

Conducting a risk assessment is an integral component of the overarching “Develop Preservation Strategies and Standards” function. These efforts are linked with the functions “Preservation Watch”, “Monitor Technology” and “Monitor Designated Community”. This guideline shows a practical implementation we have coined 'Preservation Monitoring'.

Within the context of this guideline, “Preservation Monitoring” is an evaluation method built to oversee and register changes in your operating environment and make an initial assessment of the severity and mitigation actions. This effort will then advise further “Preservation Planning” to address and mitigate the changes.

1.2. Scope

This guideline covers aspects related to performing the OAIS functions “Preservation Watch”, “Monitor Technology”, and “Monitor Designated Community”, encompassed by 'Preservation Monitoring'.

Preservation Monitoring, as described in this guideline, can be used as a recommendation on how to perform the following OAIS functions:

Monitor Technology

- External data standards
- Reports
- Results³
- Technology alerts

Monitor Designated Community

- Emerging standards
- Reports
- Requirement alerts

Preservation Watch

- Collated information about changes in environment

This guideline does not provide a framework for assessing specific file formats, software applications, technologies, or similar for use within your organisation. For this purpose, we recommended using a technology assessment framework. Several already exist and are used by preservation organisations to assess the viability of digital preservation strategies.⁴ We intend for this guideline to inform when to apply a technology assessment framework which will allow you to revise existing digital preservation technology.

While this work does mention overseeing systems and wider organisational influences on 'Preservation Monitoring', this is only to situate technological guidance and offer context. This guideline focuses on technological assessment for digital preservation. Alternative papers are available to discuss wider components within this function, such as those which discuss bit preservation⁵ and future trends.⁶

1.3. Definitions

1.3.1. Preservation risk

OAIS identifies three key reasons for data migration: cost-effectiveness, new user demands, and media degradation. These can be defined as risk drivers. If organisational processes and applications are too expensive to maintain, this creates a risk for continued operations. If your users demand something different, this becomes a risk for your continued relevance, and if media (or technological obsolescence in general) degrades, you risk losing your data.

In this context, what is considered a preservation risk?

Firstly, a preservation risk is an internal or external development that jeopardises your organisation's ability to perform its mission.

Secondly, the preservation strategy chosen by your organisation influences how risks are assessed. For example, software obsolescence has a different meaning in the context of an emulation strategy than in the context of a migration strategy.

Finally, your organisation also needs to determine its risk appetite before undertaking a proper assessment of the significance of a risk. If your organisation is risk averse you may evaluate or mitigate risks more frequently.

2. Components

This guideline defines four components as part of Preservation Monitoring:

- **Technology Mapping:** How to work out the data formats, information package standards, metadata standards, software and hardware that your digital preservation practices are based on.
- **Information Collation:** How to find out about preservation risks.
- **Preservation Risk Assessment:** How to work out the risks to your organisation's ability to keep your digital collections safe.
- **Organisational procedures:** How to get the work done.

The following sections describe how to perform the components.

2.1. Technology Mapping

This is part of a cyclical mapping of changes in technology, as explored in the sections below.

To ascertain the data, software, and hardware upon which your digital preservation practices are based, an overview of the existing technologies must be created, including the trends and wider environment related to those technologies used in your organisation for ingest, preservation, and rendering.

This involves:

- Data formats, i.e. file and database formats
- Information package standards
- Metadata standards
- Software applications for digital preservation practices
- Hardware and physical media

Obtaining full lists of the above types of technologies are sufficient to fulfil the technology mapping. The lists should be continuously updated when changes happen.

2.1.1. Data formats

It is crucial for organisations to be aware of the file formats and data interchange formats in use so that appropriate preservation plans can be created.

In order to fulfil this mapping, it is sufficient to obtain a full list of file formats, ideally accompanied by statistical data regarding the number of files contained within one's collections. It may be based on file format extensions, or preferably on file format signatures, identified using tools such as DROID⁷, Fido⁸, or Siegfried⁹.

It is recommended to employ a data characterisation tool to identify which properties and metadata the data possess and which must be preserved, or which pose a risk to digital preservation capabilities. Examples of such tools are JHOVE¹⁰, ExifTool¹¹ and MediaInfo¹².

Data Interchange Formats, also known as 'exchange formats', are crucial for the transfer of data from the producer to the archive. These formats are decisive for the effective processing of received data in the archive and must contain sufficient metadata to ensure its long-term preservation. Data Interchange Formats can be used in other processes as well, but the different use cases need to be analysed and evaluated to determine what preservation risks are important. Examples of Data Interchange Formats are for example XML, JSON and SQL.

2.1.2. Information package standards

Information package standards define how data are structured for preservation and can be used to communicate with other institutions or designated communities about what information is preserved.

Packaging formats define the structure and relations between different kinds of information that need to be preserved. By using a common specification the communication is facilitated. It also helps to investigate how complete the information packages are and this can be evaluated to see if information is missing.

You need to know which information package standards are used in your submission, archival, and dissemination practices and IT systems in your organisation. Examples of metadata standards are OCFL¹³, XFDU¹⁴, METS¹⁵, BagIt¹⁶, PREMIS¹⁷ and the E-ARK CSIP¹⁸ information package for mats.

2.1.3. Metadata standards

Metadata is vital for description, preservation, and access. It allows users to find and interpret data. From a preservation perspective, metadata enables the evaluation of the provenance and trustworthiness of the data.

Metadata standards define fields, relationships to other formats, and the data types they should be stored in. It is your local implementations of the standards that define what should be captured. For example, “Author” or “Creator” fields are typically required for provenance and findability. This metadata can be stored inside an Information Package and/or they may be stored in your organisation’s digital preservation systems. Regardless, a metadata standard is necessary to enable accessible, structured, and consistent metadata that can be exchanged across your organisation, shared with other institutions, and to your designated community.

To facilitate complete mapping, it is important that any changes to metadata schemas are communicated from the archival producer to the archive if the archive does not regulate metadata schemas in the submission process or normalise during ingest.

You need to know which metadata standards are used in submission, archival, and dissemination information packages and IT systems in your organisation. Examples of metadata standards are Dublin Core¹⁹, PREMIS, and METS.

2.1.4. Software applications

You need to know which software applications are used in your organisation for ingesting, preserving, and accessing data (capabilities such as identification²⁰, characterisation²¹, migration²², emulation²³, validation²⁴, and rendering²⁵). Like the data formats mapped in 2.1.1, they are similarly crucial in creating preservation plans.

Several general purpose digital preservation systems²⁶ exist either as open-source or commercial products. If the systems do not have the capabilities to support your organisation’s preservation plans, they may be complemented by other software for performing any of the aforementioned capabilities.

2.1.5. Technical infrastructure

Technical infrastructure is particular to each organisation. These operating environments include for example server hardware, operating systems, programming languages and DevOps pipelines.

It is also necessary to know which physical media (LTO²⁷, ODA²⁸, HDD²⁹, SSD³⁰, etc.) is used by your organisation to store the data of your collections on. The hardware, such as a drive for

manual processing or a robot for automation, determines how data is read and written to the physical media. The versions of your media and tape drives should be put in a cycle of evaluation since newer generations of the technology enter the market.

Object storage does not have a file system in the sense of a traditional storage system. It uses buckets, objects, and HTTP-based communication. It is meant to be a scalable solution without the limitation of the file system. It uses in-place data protections like erasure coding³¹.

These considerations are necessary to assess the preservation risks from your archives' operating environment, the lifespan of your storage, and the potential for obsolescence.

2.1.6. Data fixity

A technological aspect to be aware of is the importance of maintaining the fixity of data between potential data migrations. You need to perform regular checksum calculations to guarantee the bits of your data have not been changed unintentionally. Data should likewise be kept on multiple different media and locations to make sure sufficient levels of redundancy of data exist in case of disaster recovery or erroneous fixity. Significant literature and methods exist to help your organisation perform fixity operations, one notable is Digital Preservation Storage Criteria³².

2.2. Information Collation

As technological change occurs, you must know how to determine its implications for your organisation and develop the appropriate response to take advantage of general progress. It is important to monitor the technology, but also consider the community's expertise and developments, as this is the most reliable way to learn.

This section describes methods for obtaining information about preservation risks and possible channels your organisation can use to bolster its technological response as part of your risk assessment.

2.2.1. Events

Participate in conferences, network meetings, and webinars to find out about the latest developments in digital preservation.

Examples are the iPRES International Conference on Digital Preservation³³, the meetings in DLM Forum and BitCuration Consortium³⁴, community outputs shared on World Digital Preservation Day (WDPD),³⁵ and the webinars hosted by Open Preservation Foundation (OPF)³⁶ or Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC)³⁷.

2.2.2. Networks and cooperation

You may participate in digital preservation networks to find guidance on what your peers in other organisations are tackling. These networks may be national or international, and often it is sensible to participate at both levels since they support the spread of best practice to the benefit of the community. Networks can enable their members to collaborate on specific topics that drive digital preservation and for which your organisation may provide resources.

The networks often have websites, newsletters and webinars in which the latest developments are presented by the member organisations.

Examples of national networks are Dutch Digital Heritage Network in the Netherlands, Electronic Archiving Network in Denmark, and nestor - Network of Expertise in Long-Term

Storage of Digital Resources³⁸ in Germany. Examples of international networks are Open Preservation Foundation, DLM Forum, and Digital Preservation Coalition.

2.2.3. Consultancy

Your organisation knows its needs and requirements best, but sometimes it may be relevant to contract external consultants, who may advise your operations. This may relate to guidance on the status of file formats in your collections, your data quality requirements, or the applications your archive uses to support ingest, preservation, and dissemination.

Types of consultancies may include:

- Major consultancy and auditing firms
- Minor but specialised consultancy firms
- Individual consultants

You can also have your operations be advised by an internal consultant or specialist. This could be your risk assessment manager, data protection officer, legal team, data security officer, etc.

2.2.4. Academic literature review

Papers, articles, and books published by scholars and practitioners provide guidance on best practice, methods, and considerations to follow when setting up and conducting Preservation Monitoring.

Examples of academic sources you may read are “International Journal of Digital Curation³⁹”, “Journal of Contemporary Archival Studies⁴⁰”, “Archives and Records⁴¹” and “Archival Science⁴²”⁴³.

2.2.5. News and informal groups

News outlets covering topics related to digital preservation are typically organised around networks as described in section 2.2.2, but may also be commercial websites covering a broader range of information technology topics.

You may further join informal groups such as newsgroups, internet forums and blogs, social media groups and profiles, and sign up for newsletters where digital preservation topics are discussed and the latest developments are shared.

Typically, you may not refer to them as sources when you undergo Preservation Watch reporting, but these groups are great for sharing links to original content and as a starting point for further research.

2.2.6. Political, financial, and environmental changes

Understanding the factors that encourage or deter technological development is important, as it may affect your organisation's results. It can be challenging to prepare for non-technical factors that may impact technological changes, including social, economic, and political factors to enable developments that technologies require.

The cost of infrastructure maintenance may include licensing, replacing hardware, and storage infrastructure. Ensure to consult your organisational administration to receive up-to-date information on your constraints; the demand for technological upgrades could cause friction within departmental budgets.

Monitor political shifts; these could affect funding, accessibility, and your organisation's management. Tracking national or international media outlets and engaging with your designated community (see 2.2.8.) are methods for receiving this information. Legislative changes, like GDPR or copyright laws, may also affect your technological choices. Ensure your

systems comply with international standards to ensure sustainable access and migration. Your organisation's risk assessment may also be affected by changing international paradigms: for example, if your supply chain is interrupted due to political changes in another country, you must carefully consider the dependencies on which you base your preservation strategy.

To mitigate against environmental impacts, investigate and implement sustainable storage solutions, develop disaster-resilient infrastructure, and encourage eco-friendly technology practices.

It is important to encourage conversations about relevant policies, standards, and developments regarding these factors to determine the current situation.

2.2.7. Knowledge bases

You may consult online knowledge bases for detailed information about technologies, risks, and file formats. Knowledge bases are typically major websites which collate information and have a community-driven method for collating the information. Examples include PRONOM⁴⁴, Wikidata⁴⁵ and the Digital Preservation Coalition Bit List⁴⁶.

Knowledge bases may, however, also be minor scale products in the form of reports, spreadsheets, specialised websites, or other forms of collating information on a specific topic. Examples of these types of knowledge bases are the International Comparison of Recommended File Formats and DDHN⁴⁷.

2.2.8. Designated community

To engage with the designated community you can conduct interviews or user surveys. It will provide information about what changes and risks the designated community sees and finds important about preservation and usage scenarios. It might also include stakeholder observation and collaboration, workshops, and conferences. Monitoring your designated communities is an ongoing task to meet user needs.

2.3. Preservation Risk Assessment

The following chapter describes how you can assess the risks to your organisation's digital preservation capability. You can get assistance from existing frameworks like *DiAGRAM*⁴⁸, *SPOT*⁴⁹, and *CHARM*⁵⁰ for risk assessment.

2.3.1. How to assess risks

There is no specific trigger; independent knowledge is key to determining the extent of a risk. It is important to reflect on new information collated during the advisory assessment, continuously pair it with your technology mapping, and report any apparent risks. Each risk should then be assessed through the following risk matrix.

Risk matrix template

		Severity How large is the operational impact of the risk occurring?		
		Minor	Moderate	Severe
Probability	Unlikely	1	1	2

How likely is the risk to occur?	Possible	1	2	3
	Likely	2	3	3

The matrix includes a horizontal axis of “severity”; meaning: how large is the operational impact of the risk occurring, ranging from minor, moderate, to severe? Also, the vertical axis of “probability”, meaning: how likely is the risk to occur, ranging from unlikely, possible, to likely?

Risk score

The risk score is determined from the position in the matrix and its corresponding value.

- **Green** = low risk, score: 1
- **Yellow** = medium risk, score: 2
- **Red** = high risk, score: 3

The risk score may then influence how your organisation should mitigate the risk. The following risk score mitigation schemes are recommended:

- 1: Your organisation should keep monitoring the risk, unless other factors influence the decision
- 2: Your organisation should either monitor, adapt, invest, or cancel the risk
- 3: Your organisation should immediately initiate adaptation or investment to mitigate the risk

How you should mitigate a particular risk depends on the situation and cannot be solved using a formula.

2.3.2. How to mitigate risks

Any risk must have a mitigation plan regardless of the risk score; however, higher-risk scores should have a higher priority in mitigation. By selecting the correct mitigation action, a plan to resolve the risk is defined.

Many risks can be mitigated through monitoring. However, if the risk is short-term, you should consider changing the technology instead of monitoring. This adaptation also applies to mid-term risks. If the risk involves a long-term or major change, it should be mitigated by initiating a plan to eliminate it. This may involve solving the risks by investing in technology that will complement, update, or replace what is already in place.

In this section, we will consider how to mitigate risks contingent on their timeframe. Risks can be mitigated. Below, the definition of timeframes (terms) and the type of mitigation actions are described.

Timeframes

- Short-term: Risk occurring within a few years
- Mid-term: Risk occurring within 5-10 years
- Long-term: Risk occurring after 10 years

If a risk has occurred or is expected to imminently occur, this should be handled by crisis management and is not covered by this guideline.

Type of mitigation actions

Actions	Description	Timeframe
Cancel	Immediately remove the risk by eliminating the risk factor. This involves pulling the plug on old technology if other preservation strategies are available. Pulling the plug may involve changes related to transitioning to a new preservation strategy.	Short-term
Adapt	Any immediately available changes to your organisation’s operations should be planned and implemented if the risk is short- to mid-term. Specific mitigation actions may be hiring or training staff, changing your methods, and/or using new or different technologies.	Short- to mid-term
Monitor	Continue monitoring the risk. If the risk does not change status, there is no need for intervention. Implications may only happen in the mid- to long-term.	Mid- to long-term
Invest	If the necessary changes require a significant investment in resources or time, management will need to create a plan and find the resources. The plan may involve solving the risks by investing in technology that will either complement, update, or replace what is already in place. Investments may also include using an analytical framework to recommend other technologies, such as file formats, and implementing them into your organisation’s policies, procedures, and systems.	Long-term

2.3.3. How to document risks

Documenting risks connected to file formats and related infrastructure are key elements for managing data collections. Risks may be connected to storage limitations, hardware, and software obsolescence, loss in data quality, paid licences, lack of standardisation, validation limitations, dependencies to other formats, budget cuts, organisational mismanagement, or data dissemination.

Risk assessments must be properly documented so it is possible for your organisation to evaluate the assessments and track the risks as part of the Preservation Monitoring.

The following template may help when you document your risks:

Risk registration template

No.	Name	Value
1	Title	<i>Give the risk a title</i>
2	Description	<i>Describe the risk</i>
3	Risk score	<i>Provide the risk matrix score</i>
4	Mitigation plan	<i>What mitigation actions should be taken to mitigate the effects of the risk</i>
5	Risk evaluation cycle ⁵¹	<i>When should the risk and mitigation plan be reassessed (see 2.4.3)</i>

2.4. Organisational Procedures

This component describes the procedures an organisation should implement to support the operation of Preservation Monitoring.

2.4.1. Reporting

The risk assessment and advisory components should be documented (see 2.3.3.) and sent to management as a reporting outcome of the Preservation Monitoring. The fundamental reporting outcomes are cycled reassessment (see 2.4.3) and the collation of information (see 2.2). A risk matrix is important to determine priorities to be monitored more closely.

Reporting may happen as conventional reports describing the risks and collated information, or reporting may involve the use of a specialised IT system for documenting risks and mitigation plans.

2.4.2. Evaluation procedures

Preservation Monitoring enables informed decision-making and preservation planning. Your organisation should create and model processes, which support the fulfilment of Preservation Monitoring.

You may perform the following evaluation procedures:

- Map and review your existing procedures, standards, and policies
- Report preservation-related events when they happen
- Conduct evaluation meetings in a fixed cycle
- Choose appropriate mitigation actions and perform them

Processes may be described through Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) or other business modelling methods.

Example of a Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN)

2.4.3. Cycle of evaluation

The procedures related to Preservation Monitoring should be incorporated into a determined cycle, so your organisation knows when it should re-evaluate the mitigation action. Factors influencing the duration of a cycle may include your organisational risk score and the resources available.

To reliably operate, your organisation should establish evaluation cycles for:

- identified preservation risks;
- organisation procedures related to preservation monitoring;
- and technology mapping, including your file formats, software and media.

An example of a typical review cycle could be an annual Event, where your organisation's specialists and managers come together to evaluate the reports generated since the last meeting and determine which risks should be mitigated and how. Examples of evaluation cycles are: monthly, quarterly, biannually, and yearly.

Be aware, Event-based risks happen. For example, the developers of an application may suddenly announce the end of life of a product, which could lead to an immediate necessity to mitigate the risk. If so, the staff responsible for Preservation Monitoring should report and call for a meeting to assess the preservation risk. These Events are not something you can put into an evaluation cycle - unless you have an upcoming cyclical meeting where the Event may be addressed.

3. Summary

This guideline helps your organisation monitor the technology on which your digital preservation practices are set up, and assess and mitigate the risks of sustaining operations.

The guideline introduces a new term called "Preservation Monitoring", which unites the three functions "Preservation Watch", "Monitor Technology", and "Monitor Designated Community" from the OAIS standard's functional entity "Preservation Planning" into an applicable evaluation method.

The guideline defines four components necessary to perform preservation monitoring: Technology Mapping, Information Collation, Preservation Risk Assessment, and Organisational Procedures.

Technology Mapping involves researching and registering which technologies your organisation uses for digital preservation.

Information Collation involves finding out newer and updated information concerning your mapped technologies.

Preservation Risk Assessment involves defining and mitigating the risks exposed by the information collation.

Organisational Procedures describe how to set up the processes and evaluation cycles to perform the aforementioned components.

The guideline provides a list of recommended literature to better assess risks in your preservation planning.

4. References and Recommended Literature

Our bibliography contains our references, standards and software, and recommended literature which engages with the topics of risks in preservation planning and has informed the writing of this guideline.

4.1. Literature and References

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5. Postface

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